

Flipped Learning: An Approach for Millennial Learners

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Abstract

This study investigates the effects of the Flipped Language Classroom method to teach English and examine learning interest, engagement, and academic performance of the millennial generation of students. As an innovative and novel method to address millennial learners' needs for interactive and experiential learning experiences, the flipped classroom pedagogical approach was selected to teach English language skills. The Flipped Learning is defined as "events that have traditionally taken place inside the classroom now take place outside the classroom and vice versa" (Lage, et al., 2000, p. 32).

In the flipped classroom, the professor prepares short audio or video lectures, which students watch before coming to class and collect information about the lecture outside the classroom. Inside the classroom, interactive activities, experiments, discussion, peer to peer and collaborative learning takes place instead of a traditional lecture. The flipped classroom makes learners active participants and not mere passive listeners, students who are digital natives, having lower-order thinking skills or higher-order thinking skills, involved in some activities, and missed lectures can watch, pause and rewind their professor according to their own pace.

This study employed an experimental qualitative design to teach Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing Skills to the first-year students of Ganpat University, Gujarat, India. Various technological tools are used for disseminating information and assessment of the students. The data was collected and analyzed by administering a questionnaire and collecting students' feedback as responses. The result of the survey advocates that students are more interested in learning English and their academic grades and understanding have also increased by

incorporating the flipped classroom methods. To conclude, flipped learning is a much-needed approach in today's era that increases students' learning, interest, motivation, understanding, and grades.

Keywords: (Flipped learning, Flipped Classroom, Millennial Learners, Digital Natives, Interactive Tools)

Introduction

Technology can become the 'wings' that will allow the educational world to fly farther and faster than ever before; if we will allow it." –

Jenny Arledge

Technology vista has widened its horizons in the field of higher education to make learning memorable, practical, and experimental for the holistic development of students. It is a need of the time to coping up with the students who are digital natives or techno crats. For them, learning through electronic gadgets is quite experiential, interactive, and interesting. In the traditional teacher-centered teaching method, the teacher is the primary source of information who disseminate information and students become passive listeners or receiver of information. In this digital era, the traditional chalk and talk method need to be changed by some innovative methods. There is a gap between the student's expectations and teacher's teaching methods. Therefore, the flipped learning approach is a real GODSEND to bridge this gap. It is a form of blended learning that is a combination of online and offline teaching and asynchronous and synchronous activities.

Flipped Learning

Flipped Learning is a pedagogical approach used in blended learning. In the article on The Four Pillars of FLIP in Flipped Learning Network, the Flipped Learning is defined as “Instruction moves from the group learning space (classroom) to the individual learning space (home), and the resulting group space is transformed into a dynamic, interactive learning environment where the educator guides students as they apply concepts and engage creatively in the subject matter” (Definition

of Flipped Learning, 2019). The following four pillars of flipping are incorporated in Flipped learning as mentioned in Flipped Learning Network (FLN). (2014) The Four Pillars of F-L-I-P.

- 1. Flexible Environment:** Learners can learn beyond the classroom boundaries at any time, anywhere. They can access material and submit their assignment at their own pace. Teachers create various modes of teaching to enable students to learn content and showcase mastery. Learners have the flexibility in time and space where they can reflect on their learning and interact with teachers.
- 2. Learning Culture:** There is a shift from teacher-centric to a learner-centric method where learners have to learn on their own. Learners have to actively involved in classroom activities, debate, quizzes, or discussions at greater depth. The teacher creates more opportunities to engage learners in meaningful activities.
- 3. Intentional Content:** Teachers have to create learner-centered material that can be used before the class, during the class, and after the class to involve learners actively and to develop their conceptual understanding. For example, small exercises can be given immediately after watching the video to analyze learners' understanding of the concept by connecting learners with the content.
- 4. Professional Educator:** Teachers' role is more than a sage on the stage to guide on the side, a facilitator, a mentor or an observer who plan and scaffold activities according to their learners' needs and abilities to learn. Teachers continually observe and give immediate feedback to the learners. Professional educators are reflective and, in their practice, they connect with other educators to enhance their methods.

Flipped Classroom:

In Flipped Classroom the role of homework reverses from home to classroom where students discuss their problems or questions with the teacher and watch the videos related to the material before class time. Therefore, Class time is used for discussion, activities, experiments, and practice rather than delivering a lecture. The flipped classroom model is based on the idea that traditional teaching is inverted in the sense that what is normally done in class is flipped or switched with that which is normally done by the students outside of class. (Kusumaningrum & Indriani, 2017).

The concept of flipped classroom was first carried out by Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams. They both were high school chemistry teachers at Woodland Park High School in Colorado. They noticed a problem that many students miss lectures due to their involvement in sports and other activities. They also observed that students spend more time in traveling and sometimes could not attend classes. They also mentioned that students who have lower-order thinking skills face difficulties in understanding the concept. In their book: *Flip your classroom: Reach every student in every class every day* (2012), they discussed a couple of reasons why teachers should consider flipping (p.20-33): such as:

- Flipping speaks the language of today's students: It means students of 21 centuries are more advanced and quite tech-savvy who use technology for learning.
- Flipping facilitates students of lower-order thinking skills as well as higher order thinking skills to understand the concept as it integrates Bloom's taxonomy.
- It also allows students to revisit their teacher by pausing and rewinding the videos to understand the subject efficiently at any time, from anywhere.
- It increases student - teachers' interaction by giving

instant feedback in the online and offline classroom. Flipping changes, the role of a teacher from a SAGE on the stage to GUIDE on the side (Alison King, 1993).

- One of the important reasons for flipping the classroom is, it escalates Self-learning, Peer to Peer learning, and Collaborative Learning. The student involves his self to watch videos and refer the material and become active participants. Therefore, Flipping promotes active learning theory wherein student analyses, synthesizes, and evaluates information.

Millennial Learners:

Millennial Learners were born between 2001-2013 in the era of technology. They are also known as digital natives who are technology-driven. This generation of learners grew up with the Internet. They don't use a card catalog but they use Google search engine to learn quickly. They are highly motivated to learning by doing. Williams (2013) conducted a study that compared the learning styles of three different generations: Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Generation Y. Using Felder and Soloman Index Learning Style, he found that they differ in terms of visual and verbal style. The methods students used to learn in 2000 may differ from the methods used in 2020. The instructional context, cultural aspects, and rapidly increasing technology have shaped the learning styles of every generation.

Millennial learners are characterized as tech-savvy, actively engaged in social media, have experiential learning, fast-paced learners, team-oriented, engaged, and interactive, and have quite a short attention span.

Christy Price, a psychology professor at Dalton State College, became interested in millennial learners when she discovered a performance and expectation gap between the learners and their educators. (Price, 2009). She conducted a qualitative analysis and created 5 R's for teaching millennial students as stated below:

- 1. Research-based Methods:** Millennials prefer a variety of active learning methods. Their attention span is very short. Therefore, they prefer learning materials that are delivered to cater to their visual, auditory, and even kinesthetic needs. They need to experience a change in delivery formats to maintain interest.
- 2. Relevance:** Millennials have grown up being able to Google anything they want to know, therefore they do not typically value information for information's sake. They get information by simply saying 'Ok Google', 'Hey Google', or 'Hello Siri'. As a result, the teacher's role is shifting from sharing information to helping students to apply the information.
- 3. Rationale:** Millennials expect flexibility and recognize the socio-emotional rationale behind new ideas and processes. They Prefer a non-authoritarian environment where they can transform information through experiments and learn. They prefer a mentor or a guide, not a strict authoritative teacher.
- 4. Relaxed:** Millennials prefer “Laid back” sessions, a relaxed learning environment (flexible), with minimum pressure, more freedom to complete assignments, and also more freedom for personal expression and creativity.
- 5. Rapport:** Millennials strive for personal relationships. They prefer and appreciate instructors showing a personal interest in their training and development plans and achievement goals. They prefer their teachers to give immediate feedback.

Skiba & Barton (2006) state that the unique characteristics of millennials “are challenging the traditional classroom teaching structure, and faculty are realizing that traditional classroom teaching is no longer effective with these students” (p.3). Flipping the classroom addresses the individual learning styles of **New**

Millennial Learners. Therefore, it has become an increasingly popular approach to meeting the learning needs of millennial students.

Philips and Trainor (2014) suggest that millennial students have a preference for interactive and experiential learning experiences. "Flipping the classroom" is referred to as an increasingly popular approach to meeting the learning needs of this generation of college students which enhances learning interest, understanding, and motivation.

Rachmatillah et al. (2019) in the paper titled "**Teaching and Learning Transactional Dialogue through Flipped Classroom for Millennial Students in Urban era**" have implemented a flipped classroom for teaching English in expressing transactional dialogue towards millennial students (10th grades). They found that flipped classroom enhances students' interest and enable them to use various video apps like Powtoons, viva video, etc. and increase their understanding in self-learning (Rachmatillah et al., 2019).

Xin-Yu and Rongzhi (2020) in the paper "**The Flipped Classroom Teaching Method Based on MOOC is Applied to Analyze the Prospect of Physical Education**" compared the differences between the traditional teaching "paradigm" and "flipped classroom" teaching mode, and explains the advantages of MOOC. They mentioned that MOOC is an interesting way of teaching students who are technology-oriented. As it increases their interest and grades.

Method:

This study employed an experimental qualitative design to teach Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing Skills to 89 first-year students of B.Sc., BCA, and B.Tech. stream at Ganpat University, Gujarat, India. Students were assigned videos to watch before they come to the classroom. During class time, students actively participated in activities and quizzes related to the videos. Google

classroom is used as a tool for disseminating information, submitting the assignment, and assessing.

The researcher has created a video on self-introduction and assigned it to the students before the classroom activity. Students have watched the video and introduced themselves in a classroom where the teacher and other students observed and gave feedback. After the classroom activity, the same video was shared with some 'Easter eggs' i.e. interactive video. Students have to attempt a quiz that appears in a video. And then, students have uploaded their own recorded self-introduction video in google classroom as an assignment. The videos were assessed and grades were given with feedback to the students.

Figure 1: Self-introduction activity carried out in flipped classroom

Result:

The data was collected and analyzed by administering a questionnaire and collecting students' feedback as responses. The main objective of this study is to identify the flipped learning approach as an experiential and interactive to teaching LSRW skills to millennial learners. Students were asked a few questions related to the flipped classrooms to identify their perceptions regarding learning English.

The following figures indicate students' perceptions of using technology in learning English. In figure 2, 51.7% of students agreed that flipped classroom gives the flexibility to learn at any time from anywhere at their own pace whereas 29.2% said it is neutral and 10.1% strongly agreed.

Figure 2. Students agreed that flipped classroom is flexible

Do you agree that flipped classroom gives to flexibility learn from anywhere at anytime?

89 responses

In the second figure, 53.9% of students agreed that watching videos before the classroom engages them actively in a classroom. Here, 14.6% of students strongly agreed to the statement whereas 28.1% were found it neutral

Figure 3: Students agreed that watching videos engage them actively in classroom.

Do you agree that watching videos before the classroom help you to participate actively in classroom activities?

89 responses

In the following graph, students were asked questions about various learning ways. As they are digital students of this era. They preferred a flipped learning approach that enhances their

knowledge, understanding and increases their interest by incorporating innovative technology in it. They said the flipped learning approach caters to various needs of the millennial students like them.

Figure 4: Various learning needs of 21st students

Students' Feedback

Students' responses were collected and studied to know their perception towards learning through the flipped classroom. Some of the feedbacks are mentioned below.

“My suggestion for effective learning is having more activities related to the topic, more visualized and interactive.”

- **Rehan Nayak, BCA, GUNI**

“Flipped learning increases direct interaction between student and teacher. It gives fun loving environment (not only stuck to rules and regulations every time) to learn by doing.”

- **Manav Vithlani, B.Sc. IT(CS)**

“Learning through animation is always better than just hearing in Lectures.”

- **Kaushal Vibhakar, B.Tech., GUNI**

Students have shown a positive approach to learning through the flipped classroom. Even those who have heard the term first time, have demonstrated their interest to learn through the flipped learning approach.

Findings and Conclusion

The study indicates that millennials prefer interactive and experiential learning approach. They use technology for learning actively, involve themselves in the process of learning, engage in

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Findings and Conclusion

The study indicates that millennials prefer interactive and experiential learning approach. They use technology for learning actively, involve themselves in the process of learning, engage in activities, discussions, and experiments. The flipped learning approach facilitates millennials with multiple activities, games, and learning methods. It is flexible and beneficial for millennial learners who have a shorter span of attention. Flipping class facilitates all kinds of learners especially digital natives. The flipped learning approach enhances understanding of the subject

and increases motivation in learners to learn with ease. It provides more opportunities for greater teacher-to-student mentoring, peer-to-peer collaboration, and cross-disciplinary engagement. Though, minimal research has done on flipped learning in India. Researchers can explore by incorporating various educational technology at a larger scale. The flipped learning approach facilitates teachers with innovative technologies to make learning more experiential. Technology can not replace the teacher but facilitates them.

During COVID -19 pandemic, many institutes have implemented online teaching in India which was quite challenging. Teachers and learners have faced many challenges like network issues, digital literacy, and lack of resources. Still, teachers have accepted these challenges and converted them into opportunities positively. Therefore, many educators believe that the teaching practices will not be the same when the colleges reopen, there will be a drastic change in learning and teaching processes. Hence, flipped learning is an appropriate approach for teaching English to millennial learners..

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